

SOCIO-POLITICAL SITUATION OF THE KARAKHANID STATE (SPECIFIC ASPECTS)

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The Karakhanid state covered a vast territory from the Karakum Desert in the west to Lake Lobnor in the east, and from Lake Balkhash in the north to the Amu Darya in the south. The Karakhanids tried to introduce a different form of state structure and administration from the Samanids. In them, power passed not directly from father to son, as was the case with the Samanids, but from brother to brother, and then to the next generation of the dynasty. According to some scholars, the entire Karakhanid clan was the collective owner of power, and each member of the dynasty, based on his origin, could claim a part of the property of the entire dynasty. The main part of this property was considered to belong to the three great members of the dynasty - the great khagan, the minor khagan, and the Elaq khan. At the top of the state was the "great khan", usually honored with the title of "karakhan". Khans were also honored with honorary titles such as tavgachkhan, arslonkhan, bug-rokhan, along with the title of "karakhan". The Karakhanid state administration was formed from top to bottom, and the state was divided into regions. The governors of the people were called elokkhans, and the holders of this title were considered the "white khan of the people", that is, the "young khan" who were next in authority and rank to the "great khan". The leading position in the court was considered the hajib. The hajib was considered the khan's close advisor on state and civil affairs. The hajib coordinated relations between the supreme ruler and the localities. The hajibs were mainly considered the closest advisors to the supreme ruler and regional governors on state and civil affairs. This can be seen from the fact that the famous thinker and poet Yusuf Khos Khajib (born around 1020) attracted the attention of the Karakhanid Tamg'och Kara Bug'rokhan (1074-1102/1103) and received the title of Khos Khajib. He himself wrote about this: "Khos Khajib Bug'rokhan, he made him the closest person to him" [1:9]. Another important position of the court was the birin. His duties included managing palace affairs and receiving guests. The management of judicial affairs was in the hands of the qazi ul - quzzat. In the localities, qazis were engaged in judicial affairs. Thus, the Karakhanid state opened a unique page in its history and made great strides in developing the country's administrative structure.

During the Karakhanid period, the social structures of society were as follows:

- Khagan-ul-Khagan, Karakhan or Tamgachkhan. The highest official, the supreme head of state;
- Elaqkhan – a person who is next in rank to the khagan. He belongs to the khagan's family and is considered the owner of the region's property;
- iqtadors - the base layer of the Karakhanid state, representatives of combat units that carried out the main military operations. They differed from each other according to their ranks, that is, iqtadors at the level of districts and regions;
- Islamic religious leaders - imams, sayids, sheikhs, and sadrs. The Karakhanids had good relations with Muslim clergy, and the position of religious officials in the state was extremely high;

- governors, chairmen, accountants, etc. Such individuals are social strata that firmly maintained their positions during the Karakhanid period, as they did during the Samanid period;

- millers - the Turkish name for farmers, the main social stratum providing agricultural products;

- artisans and merchants - a working class of city dwellers who made and prepared various types of goods, tools and equipment of economic importance, and were famous for their trade;

- nomads - herders, that is, the main stratum that raised livestock products [2:33]. During the Karakhanid period, ordinary people were called budun, tax-paying citizens - raiyyat, tribal leaders - beks, merchants - sart. The specific features of the Karakhanid rule were that the following conclusions can be drawn from the political, social, economic, and cultural changes that occurred in Transoxiana during this dynasty :

1) a complete change in the form of ownership, the transfer of all land to the state, the abolition of peasant farms, as a result of which the term "peasant" - "village headman" came to mean the social stratum working in the fields.

2) In the vast territories stretching from Egypt in the west to China in the east, one language - Arabic - served as a cultural and scientific language. This became the basis of the First Renaissance. Also, the works of ancient Greek sages were translated into Arabic. As a result, Central Asian scholars had the opportunity to enjoy the work of ancient scholars .

3) Although the country was divided into two, the mutual relations between the two regions served well for the cultural development of the country. This was an important factor in the emergence of high-ranking state officials and poets-writers, such as Mahmud Kashgari and Yusuf Khos Hajib.

4) The ideology of Islam, which was formed as a single ideology during this period, could not exert such a great political influence on the several local states that gained independence from the Abbasid Caliphate. The socio-political and economic changes described above had a positive impact on the cultural life of the region. The sphere of use of the Turkic language was constantly expanding [3:116]. In short, the Karakhanid dynasty, which ruled for more than 200 years in the history of the medieval period of Central Asia, also played an important role in the history of the statehood of the Uzbek people of that period. According to historical data, almost all the territories of present-day Uzbekistan were part of the Karakhanid state.

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